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APPLICATIONS AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

Summary:

The article reveals the essence of the concept of "means of new information technologies. The possibilities of New information technology tools (NITT) are listed. The place of applied software packages among the means of information technology is especially noted. The names of scientists- researchers who have left a scientific legacy in the creation of applied software are brought to the attention of readers. Teaching staff in the educational process The basic didactic requirements for applied software are revealed.

Key words: applied software, means of new information technologies, application software requirements.

Implementation of information technology in the learning process

happens with the use of its certain instrumentation, which in pedagogical literature was called "Means of new information technology (SNIT)". According to Robert IV, [4] under SNIT should be understood as "software and hardware and devices,

functioning on the basis of microprocessor computers, as well as modern means and systems of information exchange, providing operations for collection, production, accumulation, storage, processing, transmission of information "[5].

The possibilities of SNIT and the range of tasks solved with their use allows formulating the pedagogical goals of using SNIT in the system of secondary and higher education. These include the development of the student's personality:

- development of thinking, aesthetic education, development of communication skills;
- the formation of information culture;
- implementation of the social order due to the informatization of society;
- intensification of all levels of the educational process (especially deepening interdisciplinary communications through the use of modern information processing facilities, including audio-video information.

Achieving the goals formulated above is impossible without a solution the question of determining the main directions for the implementation of SNIT in system of training and education. This problem is complex the nature and means of information technology can be used in as a teaching tool, a cognitive tool, a means of developing a student's personality, an object of study, a means of automating control and processing of an experiment. Among the above information technology tools, one of important places are occupied by packages of applied programs of educational appointments, which were called PPP - applied software facilities. So, PPP means an application program, designed to organize and support educational dialogue a user with a computer; functional purpose of PPP - provide educational information and direct training. Problems in the development and use of PPPs are based on a number of theoretical provisions, representing:

- pedagogical feasibility of using PPP;

-functional purpose certain types of teaching staff used for training purposes;

-typology of teaching staff mainly for methodological purposes;

-requirements for teaching staff, used in the educational process.

The pedagogical feasibility of using teaching staff in the educational the process is determined by the goals of the development of the individual's personality and based on the methodological appointment of the teaching staff. Methodical the appointment of PPP is conditioned by the need to intensify the learning process and its transfer to a qualitatively higher level. The most significant, from the point of view of didactic principles of teaching, are the following methodological goals, the most effective achievable using PPP:

- individualization and differentiation of the learning process;
- implementation of control with feedback;
- freeing up study time due to execution on a computer time-consuming computing work;
- computer visualization of educational information;
- modeling and imitation of the studied objects, processes or phenomena;

- strengthening the motivation for learning;
- equipping the trainee with a strategy for mastering the educational material;

- the formation of a culture of educational activity, information culture of the student and the teacher.

Having clarified the methodological goals and functions of the teaching staff in the pedagogical process, it is necessary to define the requirements for the teaching staff, i.e. those characteristics that will allow you to successfully develop and use these software tools. PPP requirements are considered from different points of view. Methodological requirements for teaching staff formulated in the works of BS Gershunsky [1], EI Mashbits [3], NF Talyzina [6]; psychological requirements were developed YD Babaeva with co-author EI Mashbits [2]. Analysis of the pedagogical practice of using teaching staff [5] allows conclude that the most significant reasons for creating low-quality (from a pedagogical point of view) computer programs are: partial, and sometimes complete disregard didactic teaching principles in their development; unlawful

transfer of traditional forms and methods of teaching to new technology learning using a computer. Currently, no one has raised doubts about the fact that in the conditions of informatization of education the paradigm of pedagogical science is changing, the structure and

content of education. New teaching methods based on active, independent

forms of acquiring knowledge and working with information, displace demonstration and illustrative-explanatory and methods, widely used by traditional teaching methodology oriented mainly on the collective perception of information. Parallel to this PPP is being used to support traditional methods learning. In this case, the teaching staff used for educational purposes are transferred to some extent teaching functions, therefore, each program should be built in accordance with the didactic principles of teaching, defining the didactic requirements for teaching staff. It is known that the technique teaching each subject in turn takes into account the originality and characteristics of the corresponding science, therefore it is legitimate to talk about the methodological requirements for teaching staff, which provide the specificity and originality of each specific science and the corresponding her subject. By defining the pedagogical requirements for teaching staff, it is also necessary to take into account the rationale for choosing a topic for teaching staff, reasoned with certain methodological goals, and ensure checking the pedagogical effectiveness of the use of teaching staff. Besides it is necessary to take into account the ergonomic and technical requirements for content and design of teaching staff. Based on the analysis of the requirements for PPP, it can be concluded that when developing educational software, one should pay great attention to ensuring that the teaching technology used is adequate to the processes of assimilation of information by students. It should be remembered that combined feed patterns increase the depth of information processing in the student's brain, thereby ensuring the effectiveness of training, but also excessive detail presentation attracts information that is unnecessary for a given topic, which the student already owns, and interferes with the assimilation of the required. When developing PPP, it is necessary to take into account its use in computer lesson. Hence the problem of constructing sequences of a computer lesson in terms of search the optimal number of program fragments (course frames) that need give out to the student and how many questions to ask him along the way theoretical material. In

the teaching staff, this problem should be implemented in the form of control, consisting in the organization of timely assistance to the student in case of difficulties in working with the educational material. The main principle for the implementation of this problem is the principle of interactivity of the teaching staff, which is determined by the following factors:

a) allow the student to determine the sequence (course) of the lesson in

in the case when the content is familiar to him or slight difficulty in understanding; provide guidance control by the trainee (if he chooses control, then within the control strict leadership from the program);

b) use as an alternative to the linear structure, adaptable to individual characteristics and needs curriculum design;

c) ensure the susceptibility of branching to the presentation of the training

information as questions and examples given to each to the trainee, and to track the time of demonstration of educational material, required for each student individually. For instance, a learner who has made a large number of errors when answering questions, not even more questions are required for understanding, but just longer time to read and think about the training material.

List of used literature:

1. Gershunsky B.S. Computerization in Education: Problems and prospects. - M.: Pedagogy, 1987. -- 246s.
2. Mashbits E.I. Computerization of learning: problems and perspectives. - M., 1986.-80s.
3. Mashbits E.I. Design guidelines training programs. - Kiev., 1986. -- 110s.
4. Robert I.V. Modern information technologies in education: didactic problems, perspectives of use. - M.: "School-Press", 1994.-205s.
5. Robert I.V. Theoretical foundations of creation and use means of informatization of education. Dis. ... Dr. ped. sciences. - M., 1994 -339s
6. Talyzina N.F. Methodology for the preparation of training programs. - M., 1980.-47s.